

Augmentative and Alternative Communication Interventions for Individuals with Post Stroke Aphasia: A Study Protocol to Improve Quality of Life and Psychological Factors

Priyanka V Nair *, Castroleena J

Department of Speech and Language Pathology, MERF Institute of Speech and Hearing, Chennai, India.

*. **Corresponding author:** Priyanka V Nair, Department of Speech and Language Pathology, MERF Institute of Speech and Hearing, Chennai, India. Phone:+91 9791222522. Email: priyanka.aslp1320@gmail.com.

Cite this article: Nair, P.V. J, C. Augmentative and Alternative Communication Interventions for Individuals with Post Stroke Aphasia: A Study Protocol to Improve Quality of Life and Psychological Factors. Int J Epidemiol Health Sci 2025;6: e91. Doi: 10.51757/IJEHS.6.2025.720841.

Abstract

Background: Stroke is the primary cause of low quality of life and disability worldwide. Almost one-third of stroke patients are diagnosed with post-stroke aphasia, a language disorder that hinders the interpretation and formulation of language symbols. Patients with aphasia frequently experience difficulty communicating their health-related everyday requirements. Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC) allows people with aphasia to augment or alternate communication using both low- and high-tech equipment.

Method: This was a single-blind pilot study with a Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) design, carried out in Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. Ten people with post-stroke aphasia were divided into two groups: group one received standard Speech Language Therapy (SLT), while group two received Augmentative and Alternative Communication Therapy (AACT) and SLT for ten days in a row. Participants were evaluated prior to and two weeks after the intervention to compare the outcomes. The primary result was evaluated using the Communicative Effectiveness Index (CETI) for functional communication and the Western Aphasia Battery (WAB) for overall language performance. The secondary outcome was assessed by a 10-minute talk, using the Stroke Aphasic Depression Questionnaire - Hospital Version (SADQH 10) to plan the psychological element and the Stroke-Specific Quality of Life Scale (SS-QOL) to assess overall quality of life.

Results: Individuals with post-stroke aphasia who received AACT and SLT demonstrated improved language performance and functional communication, as well as a positive impact on their psychological well-being and overall quality of life when compared to those who received only conventional SLT.

Conclusion: The study provides new insights into implementing AAC for PWA post stroke as an early and initial intervention protocol, as it allows for early recovery when compared to conventional SLT alone.

Keywords: Post Stroke Aphasia, Quality of Life, Augmentative and Alternative Communication Therapy, Conventional Speech Language Therapy, Communicative Effectiveness Index, Stroke Aphasic Depression Questionnaire - Hospital, Stroke-Specific Quality of Life Scale, India

Introduction

Stroke is the major cause of low quality of life and disability worldwide. Nearly one-third of stroke patients are diagnosed with post-stroke aphasia, a

language disorder characterized as an impairment of the complicated process of interpreting and constructing language symbols that affects auditory comprehension, reading, oral-expressive language, and writing.

Individuals with aphasia suffer varying degrees of linguistic impairment in expressions, ranging from occasional word finding issues to severe verbal communication difficulties. Language and communication challenges have a higher impact on patients' emotions and quality of life (1).

Patients with aphasia (PWA) frequently experience difficulty communicating their health-related everyday requirements. Caregivers and healthcare workers also reported problems in interacting with people with aphasia (1,2). To close the communication and language gap, PWA are frequently referred to Speech and Language Professionals for Speech and Language Therapy (SLT) (3). SLT for PWA combines cognitive therapy, speech therapy, and a variety of procedures and techniques for recovering communication. SLT, Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC) is a rehabilitation strategy that enables people with aphasia to augment or alternate their communication utilizing low- and high-tech equipment, with caregiver or clinician assistance (3). AAC tools, such as communication books or high-tech equipment, help people communicate their basic requirements, provide information and emotions, maintain social connections, and practice social etiquette (3).

The current study investigates the efficacy of Augmentative and Alternative Communication Therapy (AACT) in conjunction with SLT in improving quality of life and psychological factors for people with moderate to severe aphasia.

Objectives of study include:

- To assess and compare language performance and functional communication between individuals with aphasia undergoing AACT in conjunction with SLT and those getting only Speech Language Therapy.
- To assess the improvement in psychological factors (depression quotient) and quality of life following AACT and SLT.

Materials and methods

This was a single-blind pilot study with an RCT design, conducted in Chennai, Tamil Nadu. Ten patients with mild to severe Brocas, Anomic, and Global post-stroke aphasia were randomized into two groups (control and experimental), with five each getting a one-hour therapy session. Before starting the intervention sessions, participants will be evaluated using the Communicative Effectiveness Index (CETI) for functional communication, the Western Aphasia Battery (WAB) for overall language performance and a 10-minute conversation, the Stroke Aphasic Depression Questionnaire - Hospital Version (SADQH 10) for psychological planning, and the

Stroke-Specific Quality of Life Scale (SS-QOL) for overall quality of life. PWA in group 1 (control group) received 60 minutes of traditional Speech and Language Therapy (SLT), while group 2 (experimental group) received 30 minutes of AACT and 30 minutes of SLT over ten days. Patients getting traditional SLT were intervened with semantic feature analysis, a context-based approach, yes/no questions, and visual feedback.

The experimental group got sessions using both low-tech and high-tech AAC devices in conjunction with traditional SLT. Communication boards (low-tech AAC) featured 49 words as graphics relating to the patients' basic requirements, emotional status, medical issues, and daily activities. Lingraphica App (high-tech AAC) consists of lexical categories used in daily life with visual presentation. Patients with Global Aphasia were intervened using only communication boards, which consisted of 49 pictures relating to their basic needs, emotional expression, medical conditions, and activities of daily life. Patients with Anomic Aphasia were intervened using only the high tech AAC app, Lingraphica, which includes pictures for communication of daily living as well as a visual representation of how the words are produced. Patients with Broca's Aphasia were Regular rehabilitative procedures, such as physiotherapy and occupational therapy, were not hampered during the trial period. Re-assessment was undertaken two weeks after the intervention to evaluate and compare the results between group 1 and group 2 individuals with post-stroke aphasia.

Inclusion Criteria were:

- The Western Aphasia Battery (WAB) is used to diagnose aphasia after a stroke.
- Patients with moderate to severe aphasia (percentile score on WAB).
- First onset of stroke, anytime post-stroke.
- Between 40 to 80 years of age

Exclusion Criteria include:

- With degenerative conditions
- Other associated neurological problems
- Patients on Nasogastric (NG) Tube

Results

The study's goal was to assess and compare the efficacy of augmentative and alternative communication combined with traditional speech and language therapy in people with post-stroke aphasia. The study included ten patients and their primary caretaker, who were chosen based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. The patients were placed into two groups: the experimental group, which received AACT mixed with Conventional SLT, and the control group, which received simply Conventional SLT.

Table 2 reveals that before to intervention, patients had poor ratings in language performance, functional communication, quality of life, and depression quotient.

Table 3 shows that patients in the experimental group (group 2) who received AACT combined with SLT, as well as the control group who received only SLT, improved significantly after the intervention.

Table 4 demonstrates a clinically meaningful increase in patients' psychological variables and quality of life. Following the intervention, the experimental group showed significant progress in functional communication, as well as overall language performance improvement.

Discussion

This protocol covers a pilot randomized controlled experiment that has the potential to benefit persons with post-stroke moderate to severe aphasia who are receiving inpatient rehabilitation. The trial's major goal is to look at the efficacy of AACT in combination with standard SLT in communication/language recovery. It will also investigate the viability of scaling AAC for larger studies and therapeutic applications. While AACT has been around for decades in industrialized countries, it is relatively new in most developing countries, including China. If the experiment is possible, the study's findings may be applied to subsequent trials. People with aphasia have a lower quality of life, poorer health outcomes, and less participation in medical contacts, according to evidence. These people are more prone to encounter unfavorable medical occurrences (e.g., medication errors) than those without a communication problem. AACT may be the solution to improve the problem. AAC can help people with post-stroke aphasia communicate more effectively when spoken communication abilities fail (1,2).

AAC, as a primary intervention for people with moderate to severe aphasia, can be utilized in the early phases of treatment to improve patients' quality of life

and minimize depression (4,5). This study used AAC in conjunction with standard SLT to examine the progress of people with aphasia in terms of quality of life and psychological characteristics. AAC can be used to address PWA's immediate communication issues following stroke (2). Deprivation of language abilities during the early phases may be a risk factor that leads to poorer medical management. As a result, AAC can help people with post-stroke aphasia communicate more effectively (5). Providing AAC assistance in the early stages increases patients' motivation to communicate their needs and wants while also reducing psychological aspects associated with communication deprivation (5).

The results after two weeks of intervention demonstrated that PWA who received AACT in conjunction with SLT expressed more functional words than PWA who received simply Conventional SLT. When examined with the WAB-Bedside Record Form, these patients' receptive and expressive vocabulary improved overall. The effectiveness of AACT combined with SLT was tested using the Communicative Effectiveness Index (CETI), which demonstrated a consistent change in score over +12 that the test tool's designers acknowledged as meaningful.

A 10-minute conversation, the 10-item Hospital version of the Stroke Aphasic Depression Questionnaire (SADQH-10) and the Stroke-Specific Quality of Life Scale (SS-QOL) collected post 2 weeks of intervention showed that 60% of the patients in the experimental group (AACT combined with SLT) had improved scores in the SS-QOL but will still constitute into the symptoms of depression, whereas patients in the control group (Conventional SLT) had a minimal improvement in the SS. The pre and post-intervention SADQH-10 scores improved, indicating a decrease in the depression quotient.

Thus, the study provides fresh insights into applying AAC for PWA following stroke as an early and initial intervention procedure, as it allows for early recovery from aphasia symptoms as compared to standard SLT alone.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the participants

Demographic Variable		Group				Total	
		Experiment		Control		N	%
		N	%	N	%		
Age	< 60	2	40.0%	2	40.0%	4	40.0%
	> 60	3	60.0%	3	60.0%	6	60.0%
	Mean ± SD	68 ± 13.638		64.40 ± 14.571		66.20 ± 13.440	
	Min – Max	54 - 84		46 - 80		46 - 84	
Gender	Female	4	80.0%	2	40.0%	6	60.0%
	Male	1	20.0%	3	60.0%	4	40.0%

Table 2. Depicts the pre-intervention values of the control and experimental group based on Western Aphasia Battery (WAB), Communication Effectiveness Index (CETI), Stroke Aphasic Depression Questionnaire, Hospital version-10 (SADQH-10) and Stroke-Specific Quality of Life Scale (SSQOL)

Pre Intervention	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t – Value (P - Value)
WAB	Experiment	5	1.80	.837	0.000 (1.000)
	Control	5	1.80	.837	
CETI	Experiment	5	40.40	17.038	0.021 (0.984)
	Control	5	40.20	12.418	
SADQH	Experiment	5	10.00	2.550	0.383 (0.712)
	Control	5	9.40	2.408	
SS-QOL	Experiment	5	70.00	26.458	0.255 (0.805)
	Control	5	76.00	21.909	

Table 3. Represents the post-intervention values of the control and experimental group based on Western Aphasia Battery (WAB), Communication Effectiveness Index (CETI), Stroke Aphasic Depression Questionnaire, Hospital version-10 (SADQH-10) and Stroke-Specific Quality of Life Scale (SSQOL)

Post Intervention	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t – Value (P - Value)
WAB	Experiment	5	1.80	.837	0.000 (1.000)
	Control	5	1.80	.837	
CETI	Experiment	5	66.20	13.084	2.106 (0.068)
	Control	5	51.40	8.706	
SADQH	Experiment	5	13.80	3.033	2.150 (0.064)
	Control	5	10.40	1.817	
SS-QOL	Experiment	5	94.00	32.288	1.032 (0.332)
	Control	5	76.00	21.909	

Table 4. Illustrates the comparison between the pre and post intervention findings based on Western Aphasia Battery (WAB), Communication Effectiveness Index (CETI), Stroke Aphasic Depression Questionnaire, Hospital version-10 (SADQH-10) and Stroke-Specific Quality of Life Scale (SSQOL)

Comparison	Intervention	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t – Value (P - Value)
WAB	Pre	5	1.80	.837	-
	Post	5	1.80	.837	
CETI	Pre	5	40.20	12.418	-5.642 (0.005)*
	Post	5	51.40	8.706	
SADQH	Pre	5	9.40	2.408	-2.236 (0.089)
	Post	5	10.40	1.817	
SS-QOL	Pre	5	66.00	23.022	-3.162 (0.034)*
	Post	5	76.00	21.909	

Conclusion

This pilot study demonstrates the potential benefits of combining AACT with traditional SLT in improving rehabilitation outcomes for people with post-stroke aphasia. The findings indicate that combining AACT with SLT not only improves language proficiency and functional communication, but also has a favorable influence on psychological well-being and overall quality of life when compared to utilizing SLT alone. Participants who received AACT and SLT demonstrated greater increases in communication efficacy, lower levels of depression, and higher quality of life, highlighting the importance of a multimodal approach to therapy.

These findings support the early introduction of AACT as part of the standard therapeutic approach for PWA. Furthermore, speech-language pathologists (SLPs) and primary caregivers can support more effective and thorough rehabilitation, resulting in faster recovery and a lower emotional and psychological burden from aphasia. Future research with bigger sample numbers and longer follow-up periods is needed to corroborate these findings and improve intervention techniques for people with aphasia.

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